

GIANTLEAP

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Control system
specification and
algorithms

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Abstract: This report describes a set of prognostics and health management functions that shall be added to the basic control functions of the Giantleap Fuel Cell system. There is a close interaction of the work packages for diagnostics (WP1), prognostics and remaining useful life prediction (WP2), and integration of the full Fuel Cell System, including the BEG Control system with the basic control and monitoring functions (WP5).

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1 Fuel Cell System Overview

The Giantleap project develops a fuel cell system that is placed in a trailer and acts as a range extender for an electric bus. The bus batteries can then be continuously charged from the Fuel Cell during driving, and the bus becomes thereby independent of charging stations during operation.

Figure 1: Electric bus with the Giantleap Fuel Cell system in the trailer (indicated with the blue rectangle)

The overview of the fuel cell system topology is shown in Figure 2. The electrical interface, as seen from the bus, shall be the same as for any ordinary charging station. The main components of the fuel cell system are fuel cell stacks, hydrogen storage, DC/DC converters, air compressor, humidifier, cooling system, and the Fuel Cell Control Unit (FCCU) with necessary sensors, actuators and control software to realise the desired operating conditions and interfaces to the bus system.

Figure 2: Topology of the Giantleap Fuel Cell System

The main purpose of the basic control system is to ensure that the demanded power output is delivered by regulating compressor speed, pumps and throttle valves to maintain pressure and temperatures at the optimal values for system operation at each load level. In addition, it must be ensured that operating constraints are fulfilled, and if necessary limit the power production or even shut down the system gracefully if the defined limits are exceeded.

The FCCU provides all sensor data that also can be utilised by Prognostic and Health Management (PHM) functions.

2 Technical-Economic Considerations

The main economic impact of measures that can increase the technical lifetime or Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of equipment is reduction of the cash flow related to purchase and replacement. In a modular system, this may be used separately for the main components or the system as a whole.

During operation of the fuel cell in the bus, the power demand can be regarded as given by the bus requirement. The energy efficiency is defined as the actual hydrogen consumption per electric energy unit delivered to the bus.

The degree of freedom in operation is related to how the fuel cell operating conditions are selected and how the charging protocol is implemented. The averaged required power production is determined by the bus consumption, but how this average is achieved is subject to optimisation.

There is a trade-off between the momentary optimisation of efficiency and the impact on the degradation and thereby the RUL. The sensitivity from a change in the operating point to the degradation rate is complex as there are several degradation mechanisms.

Hydrogen consumption can be calculated via the measurements of tank pressure and temperature. Correlations for hydrogen compressibility as function of pressure and temperature are available, and from that the mass of consumed hydrogen during operation can be calculated if the total volume is known. The accumulated power delivered from the stack can be calculated from current and voltage measurements. Similarly, the net power delivered from the FC system to the bus can also be retrieved. This allows for monitoring of both stack and system efficiencies.

Charging the bus at ordinary charging stations is normally cheaper than using the fuel cell system, so a cost-saving option is to charge the bus fully from the grid at the depot during the night and plan arrival at the depot the next evening with almost empty batteries; this will replace one full charging cycle with hydrogen with usual electricity supply¹. However, the main advantage of the Fuel Cell range extender is just what the name suggests: to have the bus operational all day without charging breaks plus the ability for usage in regions with limited charging possibilities, e.g. for regional bus lines.

¹ This should however be weighed against the reduction in lifetime of the battery pack due to operation at very high or very low states of charge, even if battery prognostics is outside of the scope of Giantleap.

3 Control Hierarchy

The following main levels are defined for the control and monitoring functions of the fuel cell system.

1. Regulatory Control
2. Performance monitoring and prediction
3. PHM feedback
4. On-line vs off-line functions

The following sections gives a brief description of each level.

3.1 Regulatory Control

The Fuel Cell Control Unit (FCCU) handles all **measurements and actuating devices** for the complete fuel cell system including the stacks, hydrogen storage, all necessary balance-of-plant (BoP) components, external communication with the bus system and operator interaction. The FCCU hardware unit and on-board control software is delivered by BEG in work package 5 in Giantleap; the unit is a proven automotive component, and has been selected for having capabilities suitable for the requirements of the fuel cell system. Its basic functions are:

- Process interface, sequencing and basic control functions;
- Process measurements and manipulative outputs, system communication and remote access;
- Establishment and maintenance of operating conditions and handling of transients in presence of real-world disturbances and uncertainties;
- Process monitoring, constraint handling and emergency handling:
 - E.g.: Limit power production if cooling capacity reaches its maximum;
 - Initiate shutdown sequence if any critical limits are exceeded;
- Sequencing and operational mode management:
 - Start-up and shutdown sequences;
 - Transitions between different operating modes, including special PHM ones;
- Charging protocol:
 - The fuel cell system shall deliver power to the bus according to the bus' power demand, as if the FCS were an ordinary charging station;
 - The charging power can be relatively freely chosen when bus batteries are charged above a certain minimum (or below a certain maximum); charging may be implemented in different ways, as long as the average power is sufficient;
- Optimised scheduling based on FC performance test data:
 - Air pressure setpoint as function of delivered power;
 - Air flow rate setpoint as function of delivered power;
 - Coolant inlet and delta temperature setpoints as function of delivered power;
 - Feedback control loops adjusting compressor speed, coolant flow rate and temperature, to reach the specified setpoints;
 - Operating constraints may limit available power;
 - Avoidance of operating regions known to be damaging to the cell;
- Data logging of time series data to storage unit for off-line analysis.

In addition to these basic functions, additional PHM functions can be added via software.

3.2 Performance Monitoring and Prediction

The functions in the basic control system is the minimum requirement to realize a functioning fuel cell system. On top of the basic control system, a PHM module is added to obtain more specific knowledge of the health state, and if possible, to use the available information to enhance the operation to prolong the remaining useful life of the system and system's components.

The main basis for PHM functions is based on data from operation of the FC system. The functions are divided into two main groups:

- **Passive information gathering** without interfering with the normal operation. Store trends and parameters for remote analysis and calculation of performance measures. It is simple to implement by defining an input data set, but the information content may be somewhat limited, since some operating regions and transient conditions are rarely visited.
- **In-situ experimentation** for active stimulation of the FC system. Used to ensure that important information can be extracted and both dynamic and static performance parameters can be inferred. This on-line testing must be coordinated by the basic control system and respect the requirement of charging demand.

The data can be used for calculation and trending of vital performance parameters, and also for RUL model updating and RUL prediction.

The Giantleap FC system pilot is meant to develop into a **commercial product**, not a laboratory system: some of the measurements and data rates that can be used for FC characterisation in a laboratory will not be available in the production system, such as electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) or high-resolution oscilloscopes. However, based on the design of prognostic methods and experimental data analysis, it may be decided to introduce additional sensors in the system, if these bring a significant benefit to PHM and are reasonably priced.

A set of performance monitoring functions have been defined by Petrone in deliverable D2.1. Some of these may be implemented in the basic FCCU, but computational limitations indicate that most will have to be run off-line: the recorded data will be uploaded to a central server, where the data will be analysed. This process may be run automatically daily, for example when buses are returned to the depot for the night. As the prognostic functions are mostly concerned with long-term degradation, a centralised daily (or even weekly) calculation will not cause issues, and will bring the benefit of centralised data collection, consistent calculations (no different software versions in different buses) and ease of compiling statistics on degradation of multiple systems.

3.3 PHM Feedback

The final objective is to adjust the operation of the FC system to achieve the optimal lifetime-performance balance based on information about how the actual system has degraded. Any implementation of such changes needs to use the available degrees of freedom in operation.

In steady-state operation this for example can be:

1. To alter the pressure and temperature schedule;
2. To alter the operational limits (e.g. max current, max/min temperature and pressure).

The key challenge is to find the sensitivity of the RUL prediction from these operational parameters: this is considerably more difficult than optimising the momentary performance.

For example, higher pressure leads to improved stack performance, but also higher compressor power consumption: the momentary optimal pressure can be found by testing the FC system in operation.

However, an operating point maximising momentary system efficiency could actually lead to a reduction of RUL, and thereby to an overall loss, when considering both operating and investment costs. To properly determine the PHM control actions, the RUL prediction model must therefore contain the sensitivity of the RUL from adjustable operating conditions like pressure and temperature.

Note that, for the Giantleap range extender, the average charging demand depends on bus requirements and is not freely chosen: this may be different in other applications.

Some easily isolated feedback operations with minimal influence on long-term degradation may be moved to the regulatory-control level, if their implementation is simple and if they are important enough in the short term; for example, humidity control must be maintained at all times, and is a good candidate for implementation in the regulatory level.

3.4 On-line vs. off-line implementation

The FCCU is a well understood and extensively tested unit, but it is not a particularly powerful computer and is inappropriate for analysis of large datasets. It is therefore important to prioritise the implementation of PHM functions so that it can be decided which have to be run continuously and which can be run occasionally or off-line.

The FCCU system has a significant logging capability, and is programmed to upload all recorded data to a central server as soon as a certain WiFi signal is detected (this is typically when the bus is taken back to the depot). Therefore, data will usually become available for computationally intensive off-line operations with about one day of delay.

The functions that must be implemented **online** are those that are critical for the system's operation, such as low-level safety safeguards, but also simple analyses such as humidity control (see section 4.5) whose output is useful only if immediately acted upon. Functions that require internal feedback, such as the Poor Man's EIS (section 4.2), must obviously be implemented online as well.

Functions that implement the sampling of data under specific, induced conditions (such as polarisation curves) can either be implemented online, or applied externally during maintenance.

Functions whose operating time frame is larger, such as prognostics and rejuvenation, do not need to be run continuously, and may be preferably run **offline**: the data from the entire bus fleet may in fact be analysed simultaneously to achieve better insight, e.g. on the effect on degradation of different usage patterns on different fuel-cell systems.

The gathering and analysis of large data sets from the various fuel-cell systems may be outsourced to specialised data-analysis companies, which will be tasked with monitoring the health condition of the bus owner's fleet. These companies' access to large data sets from multiple users may increase their reliability as they deploy tools exploiting machine learning and big data, which may be outside the competences of a bus operator.

4 PHM Functions & Procedures

4.1 Polarisation curve recording

A procedure for the sampling of polarisation curves was presented in Giantleap's deliverable D1.2 (Oyarce, 2017, § 6.1); this procedure can be automated in the FCCU and regularly performed at times when operation allows, e.g. after returning the bus to the depot, but before starting battery charging, so that the battery can act as the stacks' load and no additional equipment is required.

Some sampling points in a polarisation curve may promote degradation of the catalyst or its support, in particular at high cell voltages (e.g. over 800 mV). To minimise degradation, the sampling method may avoid high-voltage areas, and measure only part of the polarisation curve; the exact parameters to decide which areas to avoid depend on the specification of the stack vendor.

4.2 Poor Man's EIS

Pivac et al. (2017, §2.2.3), in Giantleap's deliverable D1.4, identified the EIS spectrum's low-frequency intercept with the real axis as an appropriate prognostic variable to assess the current degradation state of a fuel cell. This point is visible in Figure 3 as the rightmost point of all EIS spectra.

Figure 3: EIS spectrum of a fuel cell at Beginning of Life (BoL) and after 5000 cycles of Accelerated Stress Test.

However, measuring a full EIS spectrum with customary EIS sampling equipment is inconvenient, since this equipment is cumbersome, expensive and requires long sampling sessions, often operated by dedicated personnel. An alternative is to focus only on the one point of interest, the low-frequency intercept, and measure it automatically by using a relay feedback.

4.2.1 Relay Feedback

The relay feedback is an old on-line technique used for decades in control engineering to easily and safely determine important dynamic properties from processes for the purpose of controller tuning e.g. within an *autotuner* (Åström, 1995). A relay is a simple operator, which conceptually implements the *signum* function: with e as its input, the function describing the relay is simply:

$$R(e) = \text{sgn}(e) = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } e > 0 \\ -1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

When the relay is inserted in a feedback loop, in front of a generic single-input, single-output (SISO) dynamic system $G(s)$, as shown in Figure 4, the system naturally induces oscillations that converge to the system's frequency at a phase lag of 180° (so-called *ultimate frequency*). (Provided that the process gain and phase characteristics is decreasing with increasing frequency in the area around the ultimate frequency. This is normally valid for most real processes.) Measuring the amplitudes of the oscillations at input and output of the system, one can calculate the *ultimate gain* of the dynamic system, which together with ultimate frequency is the input to the commonly used Ziegler-Nichols tuning rules for PID controllers.

Figure 4: Classical relay feedback layout for estimation of ultimate frequency and gain.

4.2.2 Adapting Relay Feedback to Low-Frequency Resistance Measurement

As per common practice in process control, where the main task is to keep a process at a set point despite disturbances, the diagram of Figure 4 assumes **normalised variables**, i.e. they are set to 0 at the nominal steady-state point. In a fuel cell, this is equivalent to operating with deviation variables such as δI and δV . The output of the relay, $R(\delta V)$, should be scaled appropriately so that its output δI is large enough to be set with good precision, yet small enough so it causes no nonlinear effects to appear nor otherwise disrupts operation; 1 to 10 mA/cm² is likely a good range, depending on requirements.

Relay feedback assumes that process $G(s)$ has positive gain, i.e. that a sustained positive input will eventually result in a positive output. The opposite is true for fuel cells, since an increase in current will result in a lower voltage, but this is easily remedied by **changing the sign** of the relay.

The relay feedback setup must then be modified, since the original version of Figure 4 converges naturally at the frequency corresponding to a **180°** phase lag in $G(s)$, whereas the low-frequency intercept is on the positive side of the real axis, i.e. **0°** . Furthermore, there are actually three positive real-axis intercepts in the EIS diagram of Figure 3:

1. The high-frequency resistance (HFR), corresponding to ohmic resistance, typically at a frequency of several kHz² (HFR);
2. The steady-state resistance (R), combining the ohmic and activation resistances, by definition at zero frequency;
3. The low-frequency resistance (LFR), combining ohmic, activation and catalyst-layer resistances, typically at a frequency of about 1 Hz.

It is necessary to ensure that the relay feedback converges to the last one.

² In theory, the HFR should have *infinite* frequency; however, due to the small inductances in some components, including external ones such as connecting cables, this value will in practice be finite, however high.

If $G(s)$ is regarded as the fuel cell impedance, the phase never crosses -180° , so the relay feedback will not reach a stable limit cycle oscillation. However, we apply **two subsequent integrators** in the feedback loop: this method still results in a 180° phase change of $G(s)/s^2$ when the phase of $G(s)$ is 0° and also filters out high frequencies, since integrators have the general property of adding a phase lag of 90° to the input signal and of dampening higher frequencies. As the role of the relay is effectively that of an "amplitude reset" for its input signal, only the lowest oscillation frequency will be able to perpetuate itself in the loop, once the higher frequencies are filtered out by the two integrators: thereby, the induced oscillation will be the one corresponding to the LFR. The layout is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Modified relay feedback to converge to the system's frequency at zero phase lag and filter out high frequencies.

4.2.3 Parameter and Bias Estimation

The system outlined in Figure 5 is conceptually complete, but there are two disturbances that must be accounted for:

- The voltage measurement is subject to noise, which may be assumed to be normally distributed; the exact amplitude of the noise is typically provided by the sensor manufacturer.
- In a real fuel cell, voltage at steady state can drift over time because of slow degradation or rejuvenation processes. It is therefore necessary to estimate and correct for a constant bias in voltage, so that the relay actually switches in the presence of oscillations in output voltage.

These disturbances can be compensated by an algorithm that provides estimates of both LFR and voltage bias, as shown in Figure 6:

Figure 6: Further modification of the relay feedback to account for random noise and measurement bias.

The estimator for low-frequency resistance \tilde{R}_{LF} and voltage measurement bias \tilde{V}_{bias} is implemented by defining an estimation error, which depends linearly on both estimates:

$$\varepsilon = \delta V - \tilde{R}_{LF} \delta I - \tilde{V}_{bias}$$

The estimates are then obtained by the formulae:

$$\tilde{V}_{\text{bias}} = \int k_V \varepsilon dt$$

$$\tilde{R}_{LF} = \int k_R \delta I \varepsilon dt$$

Where k_V and k_R are appropriately chosen positive constants for the estimation algorithm (higher values give faster convergence, lower values give more stable results). It is easily proven by derivation with respect to time that both expressions converge to one value, since the time derivative of each parameter depends on the parameter itself multiplied by a negative coefficient; the extra δI in the expression for the LFR estimate is added because δI has a variable sign during operation. The method is based on the well-known gradient method (Ioannou and Sun, 1995), where the estimate is adjusted in a direction minimising the gradient of the fitting objective (i.e. to minimize the square of the error).

4.2.4 Simulation Results

The relay-feedback method outlined in this section was implemented and simulated in Matlab Simulink with the layout presented in Figure 7:

Figure 7: Simulink implementation of the relay feedback algorithm.

In Figure 7, an additional low-pass filter was added between relay and fuel cell, in order to model actuator dynamics; this low-pass filter is then cancelled with a corresponding zero ($0.5s + 1$), installed on one of the two integrators so that the transfer function is realisable.

The fuel cell is modelled as an equivalent circuit with values for capacitances, inductances and resistances as modelled by Pivac et al. (2017), producing a value of impedance as a function of frequency, i.e. a transfer function.

Running the program of Figure 7 produces the results plotted in Figure 8. It is noticeable how the algorithm is able to converge to an estimate for the LFR and voltage bias already within 7 seconds from starting; as the voltage drifts in much longer time scales, the hypothesis of using a constant bias is confirmed to be reasonable. Indeed, the transient in relay amplitude is still far from fully stabilised by the time a good approximation of the LFR is already available.

A possible weakness of this approach could be the presence of significant **delays**, as those cannot simply be cancelled by combining an opposite zero with an integrator, and would inevitably degrade the performance of the algorithm. To significantly degrade performance, a delay should be close to the order of magnitude of the LFR frequency, i.e. larger than 0.1 s.

Figure 8: Simulation results for the relay-feedback LFR estimation algorithm. From the top, the plots show 1. The relay input (yellow) and output (magenta), 2. The filtered system input, 3. The measured fuel-cell voltage, 4. The estimated LF resistance, and 5. The estimated bias.

4.3 Poor Man's Prognostics

A simplified approach to stack prognostics is suggested in order to provide a baseline against which to compare other more sophisticated methods; this method is quite naïve and makes use only of current and voltage data during operation.

It is assumed that the stack can be modelled with only two parameters, like a Thévenin equivalent circuit:

$$V = a + b I$$

Where a and b are two appropriate parameters. This linear model is acceptable only in the ohmic region of the polarisation curve, which is however the most interesting one for performance prognostics.

The data samples for voltage V and current I of an appropriate time window are then used to calculate least-squares estimates of a and b : typically, the data from the last 24 hours of operation would be used, filtered for data points outside of the ohmic range and outside nominal operation.

Having an estimate for a and b over time, it is possible to perform a second-level least-squares analysis of each of the parameters over time; typically, a larger time window would be considered for this operation, e.g. a week, a month, or for all available data history.

Assuming the end of life is defined as reaching a minimum voltage V_{EoL} at a nominal operating current I_0 , the RUL of the stack can be estimated as:

$$RUL = \frac{V - V_{EoL}}{dV/dt} = \frac{a + b I_0 - V_{EoL}}{da/dt + db/dt I_0}$$

This calculation can easily be implemented both offline and online, providing a rough estimate of the residual useful life. To limit the computational overhead, parameters a and b should be calculated once a day instead of continuously.

4.4 Stack Regeneration/Rejuvenation

In the previous FCH JU project SAPHIRE, it was noticed and verified that some conditions were leading to a recovery of voltage degradation in a 1 kW stack (Tjønnås et al., 2016).

In a first long-term test of two stacks (over 3000 hours), problems in the I/O interface caused frequent crashes in the computer running the experiment, prompting automatic emergency shutdowns. One of the two systems was more exposed to this problem, with about a shutdown every two days, while the other experienced shutdowns with intervals of one or two weeks.

At the end of the experiment, it was noticed that the voltage degradation of the system with few shutdowns had degraded only $0.2 \mu\text{V/h}$ per cell (compared to the previously nominal value $2 \mu\text{V/h}$), and the one with more shutdowns had actually *increased* at an average rate of $4 \mu\text{V/h}$. Since these cells had been already run in the field for over 5000 hours, the possibility of an initial transient was excluded.

After analysis and improvement of the experimental rig to avoid further random shutdowns, a second campaign was run on the same stacks: the objective was verifying the phenomenon by inducing

shutdowns on one system and not on the other. The results, reproduced in Figure 9, indicated that the shutdown procedure was indeed responsible for the voltage recovery.

Figure 9: rejuvenation effects observed on a 1 kW fuel-cell stack. Data for both systems shown with their actual dates.

Whereas the discovery was very interesting and one of the major results of the SAPHIRE project, it was not possible to investigate in detail the cells exposed to frequent shutdowns (e.g. with post-mortem analysis), since the partner providing the stacks, Dantherm Power³, had acquired them with an NDA that forbade such analysis.

The implications of stack rejuvenation are especially important for prognostics, since they may increase the RUL of the stack, as illustrated in Figure 10. Previous prognostic models did not account for the option of rejuvenation, and new model cannot yet be developed since the phenomenon is identified, but still not sufficiently well understood.

Figure 10: how RUL may be influenced by the ability to rejuvenate the stack.

³ Today known and Ballard Power Systems Europe.

Therefore, the Giantleap project foresees a specific activity on rejuvenation to be performed by FESB, and resulting in a public deliverable, D1.5, due for October 2018. The findings will, if possible, be integrated in the automotive system of the range extender, and tested before the end of the project. However, since such results are not yet available, rejuvenation will not be included in the first iteration of the control system.

4.5 Humidity (Flooding/Drying)

The controller monitors stack voltage and the pressure drop across the cathodic (air) side of the stack. The diagnostic principles of this controller have been inspired by a paper by Barbir et al., in which flooding is detected with increased flow resistance and drying with increased ohmic resistance.

In the previous project Sapphire, we considered alternatives to those approaches, since the operation of a stack presents a different situation than a single laboratory cell; these are imported in Giantleap.

4.5.1 Flooding detection

To detect flooding, we observe stack voltage rather than the flow resistance: as visible in Barbir et al., fig. 4 and 5b, flooding is accompanied by a large increase in the noise level of voltage, due to the formation and transport of large droplets on the cathodic side.

In a stack, the voltage noise of each cell is independent from other cells, which means that if each cell has a noise level of "1" (meant as standard deviation of the signal), ElringKlinger's 400-cell stack will have a total noise level of $\sqrt{400} = 20$. This means that the voltage noise from a single flooded cell is only 20 times smaller than the noise of the fully flooded stack, making early detection of flooding easier.

Conversely, air flow in a stack will always take the path of least resistance, since cells are connected in parallel to the air manifold, meaning that single flooded cells will not generate as much pressure drop – they will simply receive less air. Also, as visible in fig. 4 in Barbir et al., the pressure drop during flooding is not much larger than for nominal operation. For these reasons, relying on the pressure drop to detect flooding is not as reliable in stacks as it can be in single cells.

Initial tests on ElringKlinger stacks indicate that cathodic flooding is a relatively minor problem thanks to the good design of flow fields, and rarely occurs; however, *anodic* flooding can occur in conditions of low current, because of the passive recirculation system that was introduced in Giantleap. The same arguments used for cathodic flooding detection can be transferred to anodic flooding, and the remedial action, i.e. increasing the temperature, will also be the same.

4.5.2 Drying

To detect drying, we focus on the cathodic pressure drop. Barbir et al. showed that the air flow through a cell is always laminar, which means that the pressure drop is steady in the absence of liquid water droplets. This is visible in fig. 5a of Barbir et al, where during drying the oscillations in pressure drop all but disappear, and pressure drop decreases markedly.

Since air flow takes the path of least resistance, the effect of drying on single cells will be magnified by their lower flow resistance, and help identify drying problems early on.

By measuring the noise level (standard deviation of the signal) of the cathodic pressure drop, we can determine when drying occurs.

The method presented by Barbir et al. is based on the measurement of the membrane ohmic resistance; however, this method requires more equipment or active, more disruptive sensing techniques (e.g. exciting the stack current to measure the current slope in the polarisation curve).

4.5.3 Corrective Action

When drying or flooding is observed, the controller responds by respectively reducing or increasing the stack temperature; this is easily implemented adjusting the coolant flow in its own pre-existing control loop.

Flooding and drying do not occur during nominal operation, but usually arise from transients or abnormal operating conditions; any corrective action will therefore be inherently temporary. In a simple implementation, the controller may reduce or increase stack temperature by a fixed amount, e.g. 5 °C, or to a safe temperature pre-determined by ElringKlinger.

4.6 Advanced Diagnosis and Prognostics for Stack and BoP

UFC has presented multiple prognostic algorithms for several system components based on Energetic Macroscopic Representation (EMR) in deliverables D2.1 (Petrone, 2017) and D2.2 (confidential). These encompass the fuel-cell stack, the air line (especially compressor and humidifier), the cooling system (especially the recirculation pump), and the hydrogen line.

The reader is referred to these deliverables for an in-depth description of the algorithms.

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